

ON THE PHOTOBROMINATION OF ACETYLENE DICHLORIDE IN THE GASEOUS PHASE.

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It is well known that the unimolecular velocity constant of decomposition of nitrogen pentoxide in the gaseous phase and in various solvents is the same at the same temperature. This relation also holds good in the case of another unimolecular reaction—racemisation of pinene. But the number of cases, in which a comparative study of reactions in the gas phase and in solutions of some inert solvents has been made, is very small. In a previous paper (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1936, B, 32, 145) Ghosh and Bhattacharyya have studied the photobromination of acetylene dichloride in solution of carbon tetrachloride in 406, 436 and 546 $\mu\mu$ and in the gaseous phase in 436 $\mu\mu$ only. They have shown that the kinetics of the photobromination are the same in the gaseous phase as well as in solution of carbon tetrachloride, only the reaction in the gas phase has been found to be about 30 times faster than that in solution of carbon tetrachloride.

The object of the present investigation was to make a thorough comparative study of the same reaction in 546 $\mu\mu$.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In these experiments the reaction was followed by measuring the pressure change. The green light (546 $\mu\mu$) was isolated from a mercury point-o-lite lamp by means of suitable "Zeiss monochromat" filters. The apparatus is shown in Fig. 1. The reaction vessel C is a quartz cylindrical cell with plane parallel faces fused on (11 cm. in length and 2 cm. in diameter) and provided with two side-tubes bent at right angles and with ends grounded. One of the side-tubes is connected with the reservoirs of bromine and acetylene dichloride through vacuum stop-cocks T_1 , T_2 , T_3 and T_4 and bulbs D_1 and D_2 by fine capillary tubings. Another connection is made to the pump through a stop-cock T_5 . The other side-tube is connected to the pressure gauge.

The pressure gauge consists of a sulphuric acid manometer with a bulb blown in one end, which is connected to the pump through a stop-cock T_6 . Vacuum grease containing rubber was saturated with bromine vapour for about a month before use.

[A—reservoir of bromine ; B—reservoir of acetylene dichloride ; C—reaction cell ; F_1 — CuSO_4 filter ; F_2 —Zeiss monochromatic filter ; K—thermostat ; L—convex lens ; M—manometer ; S—point-o-lite lamp ; T_1 - T_6 —stop-cocks.]

The reaction vessel is contained in a thermostat K provided with a quartz window W through which light falls on the reaction cell. The temperature of the bath was kept constant to within 0.1° .

The last trace of air was removed from the apparatus by repeated washing with the vapour of bromine and acetylene dichloride which do not react in the dark.

Preliminary experiments showed that on an unclean surface there was sometimes no reaction and where there was a reaction it proceeded irregularly. For this, the reaction vessel was carefully washed after each experiment with chromic acid, caustic soda solution and hydrochloric acid and subsequently with water, ether and pure carbon tetrachloride, and then dried by sucking clear air through this by means of an efficient pump.

Merck's extra pure "Reagent" bromine and Kahlbaum's acetylene dichloride were used throughout the investigation.

The intensity of incident radiation was measured by means of a Moll thermopile and a Moll galvanometer, calibrated against a standard lamp tested by the "Bureau of Standards". The intensity of absorbed radiation was calculated by knowing the intensity of the incident radiation from the existing data on the extinction coefficient of bromine in the gaseous state made by Gray and Style (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1930, **A126**, 603). These authors found that the extinction coefficient of bromine vapour, calculated with the gram mols per litre as the unit concentration and using logarithm to the base 10, was 29.6 for 546μ .

The Velocity Constant of the Reaction.

The constants in these experiments are calculated according to the simple unimolecular equation,

$$K = \frac{2.3}{t} \log_{10} \frac{p_0}{p_0 - x}$$

where p_0 denotes the initial partial pressure of bromine and $p_0 - x$, the pressure of bromine after time t seconds.

All the experiments were done with the partial pressures of bromine less than its saturated vapour pressure at the same temperature, saturated vapour pressure of bromine being 26.45 cm. of Hg at 30° (Ramsay and Young, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1886, **49**, 453).

It was always found that the values of K remained constant for sometime and then began to diminish slightly with time. This is probably due to the diminution of the concentration of the absorbing bromine.

Effect of Varying the Concentration of Bromine on the Velocity of Reaction.

TABLE I.

$\lambda = 546\mu$. Temperature = 30° . I_0 = Intensity of incident radiation per sq. cm. per sec. = 1488.5 ergs. P = Total gas pressure in cm. of H_2SO_4 . $p(Br_2)$ = Partial pressure of bromine in cm. of H_2SO_4 . t = Time in seconds. $p_0(Br_2)$ and $p_0(A)$ denote respectively the initial partial pressures of bromine and acetylene dichloride in cms. of H_2SO_4 .

A. $p_0(\text{Br}_2) = 15.75$ cm. of H_2SO_4 ; B. $p_0(\text{Br}_2) = 12.4$ cm. of H_2SO_4 ; $p_0(\text{A}) = 40$ cm. of ,, $p_0(\text{A}) = 41.0$ cm. of ,,

	P.	$p(\text{Br}_2)$.	$K_g \times 10^5$.	P.	$p(\text{Br}_2)$.	$K_g \times 10^5$.
0 sec.	55.75	15.75	...	53.4	12.40	...
180	51.75	13.75	75.4	50.5	10.95	69.0
360	48.25	12.0	74.5	47.9	9.65	69.6
540	45.25	10.5	74.4	45.6	8.50	69.8
720	42.65	9.2	74.1	43.6	7.50	69.7
900	40.30	8.025	74.4	41.9	6.65	69.1
1080	38.31	7.03	74.0	40.5	5.95	67.9
1260	36.71	6.23	73.2	39.3	5.35	66.6
1440	35.31	5.53	72.4			

 $K_g \times 10^5$ (mean) = 69.3. $K_g \times 10^5$ (mean) = 74.3.

Similar readings were taken with other initial partial pressures of bromine and the results are tabulated in the following table.

TABLE II.

$p_0(\text{A})$ of acetylene dichloride = 40 cm. of H_2SO_4 . C_0 of acetylene dichloride = 0.0032M. $[\text{Br}_2]$ = Initial concentration of bromine. $p_0(\text{Br}_2)$ = Initial partial pressure of bromine. $p_{360}(\text{Br}_2)$ = Partial pressure of bromine after 360 secs. I_0 = Intensity of incident radiation in ergs per sq. cm. per sec. I_{abs} = Intensity of radiation absorbed in ergs per c.c. per sec. The significance of K_g will be found from the Discussion.

$$\lambda = 546\mu\mu. \quad I_0 = 1488.5.$$

Temp.	$[\text{Br}_2]$ Mol.	$p_0(\text{Br}_2)$.	$p_{360}(\text{Br}_2)$.	$K_g \times 10^5$.	I_{abs}	$\frac{K_g \times 10^7}{I_{\text{abs}}}$.
30°	0.000985	12.4	9.65	69.3	79.4	838.0
..	0.00126	15.75	12.0	74.5	82.3	821.4
..	0.0016	20.0	14.95	80.5	94.5	830.0
40°	0.00126	15.75	10.89	104.4	82.3	1252.0

Effect of Varying the Concentration of Acetylene Dichloride on the Velocity of Reaction.

TABLE III.

$\lambda = 546\mu\mu$. $I_0 = 1488.5$ ergs/sq. cm./sec. Temp. = 30° .

$p_0(\text{Br}_2) = 12.7$ cm. of H_2SO_4 . $p_0(\text{A}) = 20$ cm. of H_2SO_4 .

t .	P .	$p(\text{Br}_2)$.	$K_6 \times 10^5$.	$K_6 \times 10^5$ (mean).
0 sec.	32.7	12.70	34.0	34.6
180	31.2	11.95	...	
360	29.6	11.15	36.1	
540	28.3	10.30	35.1	
720	27.3	10.00	33.1	
900	26.4	9.55	31.5	
1080	25.6	9.15	30.3	

Similar readings were taken with other initial partial pressures of acetylene dichloride, keeping constant the initial partial pressure of bromine and the results are tabulated below.

TABLE IV.

Temp. = 30° . $\lambda = 546\mu\mu$.

$[\text{A}]_0$ = Initial concentration of acetylene dichloride. $p_0(\text{Br}_2) = 12.5$ cm. of H_2SO_4 . $[\text{Br}_2]_0 = 0.000985M$.

$p_0(\text{A})$.	$[\text{A}]_0$.	$p_0(\text{Br}_2)$.	$p_{280}(\text{Br}_2)$.	$K_6 \times 10^5$.	I_0 .	I_{abs} .	$\frac{K_6 \times 10^5}{I_{\text{abs}}^2}$.
20.0	0.0016M	12.7	11.15	36.1	1488.5	70.4	429.7
41.0	0.00326	12.4	9.65	69.6	"	"	821.4
60.0	0.0048	12.4	9.20	82.8	"	"	985.7
20.0	0.0016	12.4	11.24	27.2	744.3	35.2	462.7
40.0	0.0032	12.5	10.5	48.6	"	"	823.7

Quantum Efficiency of the Process.

The calculation of the quantum efficiency has not much theoretical significance in this reaction, because the velocity observed is really due to reaction chains started by the Br atoms which attain a definite value at the stationary state. However, a comparison of the number of bromine molecules transformed per quantum of light absorbed in this reaction with that of reaction in the solution of CCl_4 may yield interesting results.

At the beginning of the reaction we may take it that the reaction is represented by the equation

$$\Delta x = K_6 [\text{Br}_2] \Delta T.$$

The significance of this equation will be found from the Discussion.

Taking the case of $p_0(\text{A}) = 40$ cm. of H_2SO_4

$p_0(\text{Br}_2) = 12.4$ cm. of H_2SO_4 . $[\text{Br}_2]_0 = 0.000985$ g. Mols./litre.
 $K_6 = 69.3 \times 10^{-5}$ and $\lambda = 546\mu\mu$,

We get $\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} = 6.82 \times 10^{-10}$ Mols. per c.c. per sec.

$\therefore \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} = 6.82 \times 6.06 \times 10^{13} = 4.13 \times 10^{14}$ Br_2 molecules per c.c. per sec.

Again, the no. of quanta absorbed by 1 c.c. of the reaction mixture

$$= \frac{I_{\text{abs}}}{h\nu} = \frac{70.4}{3.6 \times 10^{-12}} \times 19.6 \times 20^{12} = 0.196 \times 10^{14}.$$

Hence the quantum efficiency $(\gamma) = \frac{4.13 \times 10^{14}}{0.196 \times 10^{14}} = 21.1.$

In Table V are given the quantum efficiency for different concentrations of bromine and acetylene dichloride at 30° .

TABLE V(a).

Temp. = 30° .

$[\text{Br}_2]_0 \times 10^4$	$[\text{A}]_0 \times 10^4$	$\left(\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t}\right) \times 10^{-13}$	$\left(\frac{I_{\text{abs}}}{h\nu}\right) \times 10^{-13}$	γ
9.85	32.0	41.5	1.96	21.1
12.6	32.0	57.3	2.28	25.1
16.0	32.0	78.6	2.63	29.9
12.6	32.0	79.9	2.28	35.0

TABLE V(b).

$[Br]_0 \times 10^4$	$[A]_0 \times 10^4$	$\left(\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t}\right) \times 10^{-13}$	$\left(\frac{I_{abs}}{h\nu}\right) \times 10^{-13}$	γ
9.85	16.0	21.7	1.96	11.0
9.85	32.6	41.3	1.96	21.1
9.85	48.0	49.7	1.96	25.3
9.85	16.0	16.3	0.98	16.7
9.85	32.0	29.2	0.98	29.8

The temperature coefficient is high.

Comparison of the Reaction Velocity in the Gas Phase with that in Solution of Carbon Tetrachloride.

The kinetics of the photobromination of acetylene dichloride in solution of CCl_4 have been studied in $546\mu\mu$, $436\mu\mu$ and previously in the gas phase in $436\mu\mu$ by Ghosh and Bhattacharyya (*loc. cit.*). They have shown that the values of velocity constant in the gas phase become comparable with those in the CCl_4 solution only when $\frac{K_5 A}{K_4 + K_5 [A]}$ becomes almost unity (*vide* the Discussion).

This happens when $[A] > 0.0045M$. The comparable results are tabulated in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

λ	Temp.	Phase.	$[A]_0$	$\frac{K_5 \times 10^4}{I_{abs}^{\frac{1}{2}}}$	Ratio $\frac{gas}{CCl_4 \text{ soln.}}$	
(a)	436 $\mu\mu$	30°	Gas	0.0052	1322.0	32
"	"	"	CCl_4	0.0045	41.3	
(b)	546 $\mu\mu$	30°	Gas	0.0048	985.7	47
"	"	"	CCl_4	0.0054	21.0	

From the above table it will be seen that in the case of $436\mu\mu$, the ratio $\frac{K_5 / I_{abs}^{\frac{1}{2}} (gas)}{K_5 / I_{abs}^{\frac{1}{2}} (CCl_4)}$ is about 32, whereas in $546\mu\mu$ this ratio becomes about 47. This divergence is due to the fact that in CCl_4 solution, the velocity constant in $436\mu\mu$ is about 2 times greater than that in $546\mu\mu$,

whereas in the gaseous state the velocity constant in $436\mu\mu$ is only 1.4 times greater than that in $546\mu\mu$.

DISCUSSION.

The reaction has the following characteristics :—

- (1) The reaction is unimolecular with respect to bromine (Table I).
- (2) The velocity constant falls slowly with time (Table I).
- (3) The velocity constant is directly proportional to the square root of absorbed energy (Table III).
- (4) The velocity constant diminishes with diminishing concentration of bromine and in fact $\left(\frac{K_6}{I_{\text{abs}}^{\frac{1}{2}}}\right)$ remains practically constant for all concentrations of bromine (Table II).
- (5) The velocity constant increases about 1.4 times for 10° rise in temperature which is also the case in solution of CCl_4 (Table II).
- (6) The inverse of K plotted against the inverse of the initial concentration of acetylene dichloride gives a straight line (Fig. 2).

The experimental data recorded above can be explained by the following mechanism of reaction :—

where A represents the acetylene dichloride molecule. The above mechanism gives for

$$K_6 = \frac{I}{[\text{Br}_2]} \cdot \frac{d[\text{Br}_2]}{dt} = K_3 \sqrt{\frac{I_{abs}}{N h \nu \cdot K_2}} \cdot \frac{K_5[\text{A}]}{K_4 + K_5[\text{A}]}$$

$$= K_3 \left(\frac{I_{abs}}{E K_2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{K_5[\text{A}]}{K_4 + K_5[\text{A}]} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (a)$$

where $E = N \cdot h \cdot \nu$.

From (a) it follows that $\frac{I}{K_6}$ plotted against $\frac{I}{[\text{A}]}$ must give a straight line which has been found to be true.

The equation (a) also agrees well with the experimental observation recorded in Table III that K_6 varies as the square root of the energy of radiation absorbed.

From Table VI it will be seen that under comparable conditions of experiment, the reaction proceeds about 47 times ($\lambda = 546\mu\mu$) faster in the gas phase than in CCl_4 solution.

The two intermediate association reactions

require generally for fruitful collisions, the presence of a third body to carry away the excess energy. In the gas phase for the same amount of absorbed energy per c.c., the concentration of bromine atoms will necessarily be much larger than in the case of CCl_4 solutions.

The effect of the increased concentration of bromine atom is, however, counteracted by the retardation of reaction (iii) due to absence of the third body. An exact balance, however, is not attained, and the net result is that the velocity constant in the gas phase is much greater than in CCl_4 solution.

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